

Binuclear Metal Chelates of Biphenyldihydrazone of 1,3-Diketones

K. KRISHNANKUTTY* and JOHNS MICHAEL

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala-673 635

Manuscript received 2 September 1993, revised 9 June 1994, accepted 22 July 1994

Reaction of biphenyl-4,4'-tetrazonium ion with 1,3-diketones (benoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane and thenoyl-trifluoroacetone) led to the formation of 2,2'-(4,4'-biphenyldihydrazone)bis(1,2,3-triketones). The compounds have been shown to exist in the intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded dihydrazones. Bimetallic chelates of composition M_2L_2 ($M = Cu^{II}$, Ni^{II} and Pd^{II}) have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of ir, 1H and ^{13}C nmr and mass spectral data.

Binucleating ligands with isolated donor sets separated by suitable bridging group have considerable importance as model compounds in bioinorganic studies¹. The Schiff base condensation reaction in one of the most widely employed method for the synthesis of such ligand systems^{1,2}. Our interest in the synthesis of polydentate and macrocyclic chelates by the reaction of arene diazonium and tetrazonium salts with 1,3-diketones and metal 1,3-diketones³ led to the synthesis and characterisation of the polydentate ligands, 2,2'-(4,4'-biphenyldihydrazone)bis(1,2,3-triketones) (**1a-c**) and their bimetallic copper(II), nickel(II) and palladium(II) chelates (**2**).

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the ligands (Table 1) indicate that two molecules of 1,3-diketone reacted with one equivalent of the tetrazonium salt. The products are soluble in common organic solvents. It has been shown that reaction of phenyldiazonium ion with 1,3-diketones lead to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded 1,2,3-triketone-2-phenylhydrazones in which one of the carbonyl group is involved in hydrogen bonding^{3,4}. The two types of carbonyl groups can be easily distinguished from ir and nmr spectra. The ir and nmr spectra of the reaction product of biphenyltetrazonium ion with the 1,3-diketones are consistent with structure **1**. Thus the ir spectra of the compounds displayed abroad band at 3 400-2 400 cm^{-1} for the chelated NH functions. The observed carbonyl stretching frequencies

of the compounds at 1 652, 1 650 and 1 705 (free C=O) and 1 628, 1 618 and 1 635 cm^{-1} (chelated C=O) for **1a**, **1b** and **1c** respectively, indicate that R_1CO is involved in internal hydrogen bonding and R_2CO remains free^{3,5}. Two medium intensity bands were observed at about 1 610 (C=N) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C). The 1H nmr spectra of the compounds are characterised by the presence of a low field two-proton signal at $\sim\delta$ 14 for the chelated hydrazone protons^{3,4}. The position and integrated intensities of all the signals (Table 1) conform to structure of the compounds. The ^{13}C nmr spectra indicate that the compounds contain only two types of carbonyl functions and both the C=N groups are in identical chemical environment (Table 1). As expected the spectrum of **1a** showed only a single methyl carbon resonance signal at 25.65 ppm.

The mass spectra of the compounds are dominated by an intense $(M + 1)^+$ peak. The spectra differ considerably from the reported spectra of 1,3-diketones⁶. The fragmentation pattern appears to resemble that of 1,2,3-triketone-2-arylhydrazones³. The appearance of a peak at m/z $(M-R_2COCNCOR_1)^+$ indicates that the cleavage occurs first at one of the N-N bond followed by the scission of the second N-N bond (fragments of m/z 182-185 due to $(HNC_6H_4C_6H_4NH)^+$ and its protonated species). Prominent peaks found in the spectra are given in Table 1. The spectrum of **1c** appeared to be complex and hence not included.

The metal complexes : All the metal complexes be-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, NMR AND MASS SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd	M.p (°C)	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
H ₂ L'(1a)	188	72.26 (72.45)	4.10 4.91	10.88 10.57)	-
H ₂ L'(1b)	198	76.59 (77.06)	3.78 4.59	7.82 8.56)	-
H ₂ L''(1c)	169	51.52 (52.69)	1.90 2.46	8.08 8.62)	-
Cu ₂ L ₂	200	64.80 (64.92)	3.76 4.06	9.08 9.47	10.52 10.74)
Ni ₂ L ₂	240	65.53 (65.45)	3.85 4.69	9.15 9.54	9.75 10.01)
Pd ₂ L ₂	198	60.28 (60.53)	3.29 3.78	8.59 8.82)	-
Cu ₂ L ₂ '	257	70.31 (70.44)	3.58 3.91	7.60 7.83	8.71 8.87)
Ni ₂ L ₂ '	300	70.70 (70.91)	3.43 3.94	7.47 7.88	8.02 8.26)
Pd ₂ L ₂ '	245	66.27 (66.46)	3.24 3.69	7.09 7.38)	-
Cu ₂ L ₂ ''	158	47.62 (47.54)	1.74 1.98	7.66 7.92	8.25 8.31)
Ni ₂ L ₂ ''	158	47.62 (47.54)	1.74 1.98	7.66 7.92	8.25 8.31)
Pd ₂ L ₂ ''	210	44.16 (44.54)	1.49 1.86	7.30 7.42)	-

1a ¹H nmr δ 2.65 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.20–7.65 (10H, m, ArH), 7.82–7.92 (8H, m, ArH), 14.80 (2H, NH). ¹³C nmr δ 144.8 (C=N), 199.5, 196.4 (C=O), m/z 531, 530, 356–358, 182–185, 152–155, 165, 95, 89–92, 77, 69, 55, 43; 1b ¹H nmr δ 7.22–7.52 (20H, m, ArH), 7.94–8.16 (8H, m, ArH), 13.86 (2H, NH), ¹³C nmr δ 145.2 (C=N), 199.2, 197.8 (C=O), m/z 655, 654, 418–420, 182–185, 152–155, 105, 95, 92, 91, 77, 69, 55; 1c ¹H nmr δ 7.45–7.80 (6H, m, ArH), 7.90–8.10 (8H, m, ArH), 13.98 (2H, NH), ¹³C nmr 148.5 (C=N), 198.4, 197.2 (C=O); Cu₂L₂ m/z 1186, 1184, 1182, 1143, 1141, 1139, 1081, 1079, 1077, 658, 656, 654, 593, 591, 530–528; Ni₂L₂ ¹H nmr δ 2.75 (12H, s, CH₃), 7.20–8.10 (ArH), ¹³C nmr δ 143.5 (C=N), 199.2, 201.4 (C=O); Pd₂L₂ ¹H nmr δ 2.74 (12H, s, CH₃), 7.20–8.10 (ArH), ¹³C nmr 143.6 (C=N), 199.5, 201.2 (C=O), Cu₂L₂' m/z 1434, 1432, 1430, 1329, 1327, 1325, 782, 780, 778, 717, 715, 654–652; Ni₂L₂' ¹H nmr δ 7.12–8.26 (ArH), ¹³C nmr δ 144.8 (C=N), 199.8, 201.6 (C=O), Pd₂L₂' ¹H nmr 7.12–8.28 (ArH), ¹³C nmr δ 149.2 (C=N), 199.8, 201.6 (C=O)

have as non-electrolytes and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for their preparation. The copper(II) complexes showed normal magnetic moment of 1.72–1.79 B.M. The nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes are diamagnetic.

	R ₁	R ₂	
H ₂ L'(1a)	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	M = Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} and Pd ^{II}
H ₂ L'(1b)	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	
H ₂ L''(1c)	C ₄ H ₉ S	CF ₃	

The ir spectra of the complexes are compatible with the structure that would result if the chelated hydrogens are replaced by metal ion as in structure 2. Thus the position of the free carbonyl band of the ligands (1650–1705 cm⁻¹) is only marginally altered in the spectra of the metal chelates (1640–1710 cm⁻¹). The band due to hydrogen-bonded carbonyl of the ligand (1618–1635 cm⁻¹) disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes; instead new band appeared at 1550–1568 cm⁻¹ assignable to the stretching of metal-bonded carbonyl group^{3,7}. The broad free ligand band at 3400–2400 cm⁻¹ cleared up in the spectra of the metal chelates, and weak bands appeared due to C–H stretching. The bands due to thienyl ring (1435 and 1410 cm⁻¹) in the spectrum of 1c shifted appreciably to lower frequencies in the spectra of the chelates. Spectra of all the chelates showed two medium intensity bands (not found in the spectra of ligands) at 518–528 (M–N) and 415–422 cm⁻¹ (M–O)³.

In conformity with structure 2 in the ^1H nmr spectra of the diamagnetic chelates, the low field signal due to NH functions of the ligands disappeared. The integrated intensities of the various proton signals agree well with the structure of the chelates (Table 1). That all the methyl groups of the chelates of 1a are in identical chemical environment is evident from the appearance of a single resonance signal at about 28.50 ppm in their ^{13}C nmr spectra. The spectra of the chelates clearly indicate the two types of carbonyl functions. Thus ir and nmr spectra support the symmetrical structure of the bimetallic chelates.

The mass spectra of the copper(II) chelates showed a molecular ion peak at m/z $[\text{M}_2\text{L}_2]^+$. Peaks due to the fragments $[\text{M}_2\text{L}_2 - \text{R}_1\text{CO}]^+$, $[\text{M}_2\text{L}_2 - \text{R}_1\text{CO} - \text{R}_2\text{CO}]^+$, $[\text{M}_2\text{L}]^+$ and $[\text{ML}]^+$ are comparatively more intense than the molecular ion peak. The base peak in all the cases is due to the free ligand. The fragmentation pattern of all the chelates are more or less similar to that of the free ligands, except that in the former several metal-containing fragments can be identified (Table 1). Such fragments can be easily located because of the 1 : 2 isotopic ratio of ^{65}Cu and ^{63}Cu .

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by coupling tetrazotised benzidine with 1,3-diketones (benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane and thenoyltrifluoroacetone). The biphenyl-4,4'-tetrazonium salt solution⁸ (0.1 mol) was added slowly with stirring to a methanol solution (200 ml) of the 1,3-diketones (0.2 mol). Saturated aqueous sodium acetate solution was simultaneously added to control pH of the mixture around 5. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from hot benzene. Yields of the ligands were 90–95% (based on 1,3-diketone).

For preparing the metal chelates, a solution of the metal salt (acetate of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} and chloride of Pd^{II}) (0.01 mol) in minimum quantity of methanol was

added to a solution of the ligand (0.01 mol) in 1 : 1 DMF-methanol mixture (50 ml). Aqueous 1% solution of sodium acetate was then added and the mixture refluxed for about 3 h. The precipitate formed on cooling to about 10° , was washed with water and crystallised from hot methanol.

Molecular weight of the complexes were determined by Rast's method using camphor as medium. Infrared spectra (KBr pellet) were taken on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrometer, nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Bruker WM 400 instrument using TMS and mass spectra on a JEOL SX-102 spectrometer (FAB using argon).

Acknowledgement

Spectral facilities provided by R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow and I.I.T., Bombay, are acknowledged.

References

1. D. E. FENTON in "Advances in Inorganic and Bioinorganic Mechanisms", ed. A. G. SYKES, Academic, London, 1983, p. 187.
2. L. F. LINDOY, *Quart. Rev.*, 1971, **25**, 379; *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1975, **4**, 431; D. ST. C. BLACK, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **9**, 219.
3. K. KRISHNANKUTTY and N. THANKARAJAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 401; K. KRISHNANKUTTY and J. MICHAEL, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1991, **22**, 327; 1993, **28**, 259; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 860.
4. A. MITCHELL and D. C. NONHEBEL, *Tetrahedron*, 1979, **35**, 2013.
5. L. J. BELLAMY, "Advances in Infrared Group Frequency", Methuen, London, 1968.
6. J. H. BOWIE, D. H. WILLIAMS, S. O. LAWESSON and G. SCHROLL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 1384.
7. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1978.
8. K. H. SAUNDERS and R. L. M. ALLEN, "Aromatic Diazo Compounds", Arnold, London, 1985, p. 30.

